

Integrated germplasm improvement-upland

Performance of upland breeding lines and germplasm under periodic moisture stress in erosion-susceptible soil

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We compared 48 advanced upland rice breeding selections, IRRI germplasm, and traditional cultivars from northeastern India with six recommended upland rice cultivars.

Soil had pH 6.8, light to medium texture (Gangetic alluvial zone), and moderate slope, making it susceptible to erosion. It had low water retention and was deficient in N, organic matter, and P.

The experiment was laid out in simple observational plots of three, 1.5-m rows/line, 20 cm apart. Rice was direct seeded 13 May 1988 and 18 June 1989. A 13-d dry spell delayed germination in 1988. Dry periods during tillering, booting, and

Some characteristics of 16 early- and medium-maturing entries under upland direct seeded condition in Krishnagar, summer 1988 and 1989.

Designation	Days to heading (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicle length		Weight of single panicle (g)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Plot yield (kg/ha)
			Mean ±	SD			
<i>Early group (<100 d)</i>							
GS	62	112.5	24.5 ±	1.36	3.5	346	4.1
Harin Kajli (traditional aus)	53	95.7	19.7 ±	1.38	1.8	385	3.1
IR47697-2-F ₄ -B-MLD24	60	77.8	19.8 ±	2.13	2.4	320	2.6
IR47697-2-F ₄ -B-MLD27	69	77.0	20.5 ±	1.42	2.3	280	2.9
Dumri (traditional aus)	51	110.8	23.2 ±	1.82	2.3	340	2.6
Dular (traditional check)	52	117.0	24.3 ±	1.47	1.8	460	3.2
IET6223 (check)	62	86.5	19.7 ±	1.59	2.3	480	2.8
CR237-1 (check)	61	98.0	24.5 ±	2.21	1.8	300	2.5
<i>Medium group (110-115 d)</i>							
IR47697-2-F ₄ B-MLD19	72	83.2	19.7 ±	1.24	2.6	388	4.0
ARC7046	76	110.7	22.7 ±	1.72	2.3	368	3.6
IR47701-79-B-14	79	111.0	23.5 ±	2.34	2.3	464	3.2
IR47701-79-B-1	78	105.3	22.5 ±	1.86	2.4	382	3.0
IR47697-2-F ₄ -MLD23	74	78.7	24.2 ±	1.43	2.4	434	2.9
Panke (traditional check)	76	116.0	22.2 ±	1.73	1.9	264	2.9
IET2233 (improved check)	74	79.3	20.5 ±	1.68	3.2	220	2.8
Rasi (improved check)	78	82.7	23.6 ±	1.82	2.7	324	2.5

flowering stages also stressed test entries. Rainfall was evenly distributed during vegetative and reproductive phases in the 1989 experiment.

Lines were divided into two duration

groups (<100 d and 100-115 d). Data were collected on the best entries (see table). Short-duration lines are generally preferred because an August harvest allows time for a wet season crop. □

BR20 and BR21: promising upland rices for Bangladesh coastal region

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In southeastern Bangladesh coastal areas, farmers typically grow one wet season rice crop. Land remains fallow the rest of the year because of high salinity. When the monsoons start early, farmers can grow short-duration, rainfed upland aus rice before the main crop, but this is rarely done.

We compared recently-released modern varieties (MVs) BR20 and BR21 with traditional varieties (TVs) in field experiments at Sonagazi station and in farmers' fields.

BR20, BR21, Boilam, and Binnatoa seeds were line-sown at 50 kg/ha after the first monsoon rains in 1988 and 1989.

The top 5 cm of soil had electrical conductivity of 8-10 dS/m; the next 20 cm of soil, 2-5 dS/m.

We also conducted trials in farmers' fields in 1989 at nine coastal district locations. BR20 and BR21 were compared with a locally popular TV (Kalimugi, Hashikalmi, or Chinal).

BR20 and BR21 outyielded TVs in both trials (Table 1). BR21 and the TVs matured in 95-98 d; BR20 matured in 108 d.

Table 1. Performance of BR20 and BR21 as rainfed upland rices compared with 2 popular local TVs. BRRI Regional Station, Sonagazi, Feni.

Variety	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)		Days to maturity
	1988	1989	
Binnatoa	2.2 c	1.6 b	95
Boilam	1.9 d	1.7 b	97
BR20	3.0 a	3.0 a	108
BR21	2.7 b	2.8 a	98

^aIn a column, figures followed by a common letter do not differ significantly at the 5% level by DMRT.

Rice yield varied with farm location, perhaps because of soil salinity differences. BR20 and BR21 yielded higher (2.0-3.6 t/ha) than the TVs (1.0-2.0 t/ha) at all locations (Table 2). □

Table 2. Performance of BR20 and BR21 as rainfed upland rices compared with locally popular TVs in farmers' fields in 3 coastal districts.

Site	Grain yield (t/ha)		
	BR20	BR21	TV ^a
<i>Feni district</i>			
Dagonbhuiya	3.6	3.0	1.8 (Kalimugi)
Parshuram	3.1	3.0	2.0 (Hashikalmi)
Chagalniya	2.5	2.0	1.3 (Chinal)
Motiganj	3.0	2.5	1.5 (Binnatoa)
<i>Laxmipur</i>			
Laxmipur Sadar	3.2	3.3	1.5 (Boilam)
Ramganj	3.5	3.1	1.5 (Kalimugi)
Ramgoti	3.0	3.0	1.0 (Chinal)
<i>Noakhali</i>			
Senbug	2.0	2.6	1.4 (Binnatoa)
Companiganj	2.7	3.1	1.5 (Boilam)

^aName of TV in parentheses.